

TREAT-AD

TaRget Enablement to Accelerate
Therapy Development for AD

SNX32

(Sorting Nexin 32)

A Target Enabling Package (TEP)

Gene ID / UniProt ID / EC	254122 / Q86XE0
Target Nominator	TREAT-AD, AMP-AD
TREAT-AD Authors	Emory-Sage-SGC-JAX TREAT-AD Center
Therapeutic Area(s)	Alzheimer's disease
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CONTENTS OF TEP

Bioinformatic target analysis: Target Source & Hypothesis

Protein constructs & expression methods: PX domain of SNX32 (S17-M197) containing an N-terminal His6-Sumo1-Sumo cleavage site tag.

TARGET SOURCE & HYPOTHESIS

Why was the target selected? This target was identified through a protein quantitative trait locus analysis.

TREAT-AD Target Risk Score: 4.29 (rank #78, 99.7th percentile)

The TREAT-AD Center has developed a target ranking score encompassing genomics and genetics evidence. The Target Risk Score represents the gene target's general relevance to Alzheimer's Disease, and is the sum of the target's Genetics Score and Genomics Score. Target Risk Score values range from 0 to 5, with 5 being evidence of the strongest association with AD. A complete description of the methodology used to calculate these scores is available [here](#). This score was taken from Agora, Data Version syn13363290-v62.

The TREAT-AD Target Risk Score for this target is 4.29 out of 5 (rank #78, 99.7th percentile). The individual score components include 2.37 of 3 for genetics, and 1.93 out of 2 for genomics. The meta-analysis of

proteomic and transcriptomic data sources used in the genomics score indicates that the expression of SNX32, both protein and RNA, is significantly decreased in brains from patients with AD.

The TREAT-AD Center has also developed a target categorization system specific to AD relevant processes, termed biological domains (biodomains). These biological domains are defined by constituent Gene Ontology (GO) terms and genes are then annotated to specific biological domains via GO term annotations. SNX32 is annotated to GO terms from the Endolysosome, Lipid Metabolism, and Autophagy biological domains.

Cell-type specific expression is assessed using single-cell expression data from the Seattle Alzheimer’s Disease Brain Cell Atlas (SEA-AD). The distribution of expression values for all genes found in each broad cell type are displayed as violins. The expression of the target in subtypes within each broad class is shown as a point. Blue points show the summary expression of cells from individuals with no dementia, while red points show summary metrics of cells from dementia patients. Open circles reflect low confidence measures of

expression. The expression of SNX32 is confidently detected in both inhibitory and excitatory neuron subtypes within this dataset.

SUMMARY OF PROJECT

Sorting Nexin 32 (SNX32) is one of the highest scoring proteins evaluated with significant contributions from genetics, genomics and literature, which maps into the endolysosomal pathway (as discussed above). However, very little is known about SNX32 function or its exact role in Alzheimer’s disease (AD). In order to promote greater investigation into SNX32 role in AD pathology, we are developing a target enabling package consisting of purified protein and a full antibody assessment including the identification of functional antibodies, validation for specific laboratory purposes, and a comparison to other antibodies commonly utilized. For greater details of the resources developed, see the sections below. We hope through the promotion of effective resources we can stimulate the future investigation of SNX32 and its role in AD physiology.

SCIENTIFIC BACKGROUND

Little is known about the exact function of sorting nexin 32 (SNX32), beyond its membership in the sorting nexin family, supporting a role in intracellular trafficking between the endocytic and golgi compartments. SNX32 shares homology with other members of the sorting nexin family, particularly SNX5 and SNX6, both of which are members of the ESCPE-1 complex, which interacts with the retromer complex to direct retrograde transport trafficking out of the endosome to the golgi [1]. SNX32 is predicted to bind phosphatidylinositol (UniProt and Entrez Gene), but the functional implications of this association is unclear. SNX32 has recently been associated with Alzheimer's disease (AD) risk in a genome wide association study (GWAS coupled with a proteome wide association study (PWAS), demonstrating genetic risk aligned with decreased protein expression, that localizes to glutamatergic neurons and astrocytes, consistent with the informatics analysis provided above [2]. Another study mapping phenotypes across neurological diseases to genetic loci also identified SNX32 as a potential regulator of AD risk [3]. This is consistent with other genetic perturbations to retromer function that also confer increased AD risk [4]. One plausible hypothesis is that SNX32 functions in association with retromer complex to alter intracellular cargo protein localization, such as APP, from the endocytic compartment, a site of high amyloid production [5], to the golgi, reducing amyloid production in the brain.

RESULTS – THE TEP

Proteins Purified

SNX32A-c014: PX domain of SNX32 (S17-M197) containing an N-terminal His6-Sumo1-Sumo cleavage site tag. This protein will be useful for crystallography and activity assays.

Fig. 1. SEC trace (left) of SNX32A-c014 with peak fractions (denoted by star on trace) run on an SDS-PAGE gel (right).

CONCLUSION

The tools presented here provide a foundation for further biological investigation of the role of SNX32 in AD.

FUNDING INFORMATION

The work performed by the Emory-Sage-SGC TREAT-AD Center has been funded by the National Institute on Aging through grant U54 AG065187.

ADDITIONAL INFORMATION

Materials and Methods

Protein expression constructs and protein purification

All relevant plasmids are available on addgene: [TREAT-AD plasmid collection](#)

Construct Details

Construct ID	SNX32A-c014
Parental vector	pSUMO-LIC
Tag	N-terminal His6-SUMO1-SUMO cleavage site
Protein mass (with tag)	33259.5 Da
Protein mass (with tag removed)	20699.5 Da
Extinction Coefficient ($M^{-1} cm^{-1}$)	15930
Protein sequence (with tag)	MCSSHHHHHHGSGSGSDQEAKPSTEDLGDKKEGEYIKLVIGQDSSEIHFVKMTTHLKKLK ESYCQRQGVPMNSLRFLFEGQRIADNHTPKELGMEEEDVIEVYQEQTGGSVDLQGDSSLQV EISDAVSEKDKVKFTVQTKSCLPHFAQTEFSVVRQHEEFIWLHDAYVENEYAGLIIPPAPRP DFEASREKLQKLGEGDSSVTREEFAKMKQLEAEYLAIFKKTVMHEVFLQLAAHPTLRRDH NFFVFLEYGQDLSVRGKNRKELGGFLRNIVKSADEALITGM
Protein sequence (after tag removal)	SVDLQGDSSLQVEISDAVSEKDKVKFTVQTKSCLPHFAQTEFSVVRQHEEFIWLHDAYVENE YAGLIIPPAPRPDFEASREKLQKLGEGDSSVTREEFAKMKQLEAEYLAIFKKTVMHEVFLQ RLAAHPTLRRDHNFFVFLEYGQDLSVRGKNRKELGGFLRNIVKSADEALITGM

Expression and Purification Protocol

Expression host	<i>E. Coli</i> : BL21(DE3)-R3-pRARE
Expression medium	Terrific broth (TB) with 50 µg/ml kanamycin (kan). Starter cultures also included 34 µg/ml chloramphenicol (cm).
Transformation and storage	Transform the construct into the <i>E. coli</i> strain BL21(DE3)-R3-pRARE, a phage-resistant variant of Rosetta 2 (MSD). Plate on LB-agar plates containing kan (50 µg/ml) and cm (34 µg/ml). Inoculate LB broth containing the same antibiotics with several colonies. After overnight incubation at 37°C, add glycerol to 15% (v/v) final volume, and store at -80°C.
Expression	Inoculate LB + kan + cm media for overnight growth at 37°C. Inoculate 1 L of TB + kan with 10 ml of the overnight culture. Grow cultures at 37°C with vigorous aeration in 2.5 L Tunair flasks until reaching an $OD_{600} = 1.5 - 2$. Shift the cultures to 18°C for 30 minutes before inducing protein expression with 0.3 mM IPTG. Continue incubation for 16 hours at 18°C before harvesting cells by centrifugation (3000g, 25 min, 4°C). Store pellets and -80°C until needed.

Purification buffers	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Lysis buffer: 50 mM HEPES (pH 7.5), 500 mM NaCl, 10 mM imidazole, 5% glycerol, 1 mM TCEP 2. W30 Buffer: 50 mM HEPES (pH 7.5), 500 mM NaCl, 30 mM imidazole, 5% glycerol, 1 mM TCEP 3. Elution Buffer (EB): 50 mM HEPES (pH 7.5), 500 mM NaCl, 300 mM imidazole, 5% glycerol, 1 mM TCEP. 4. SEC buffer: 50 mM HEPES (pH 7.5), 500 mM NaCl, 5% glycerol, 1 mM TCEP 5. Ni-sepharose beads, equilibrated in Lysis buffer.
Purification step 1: IMAC	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Resuspend thawed pellet in lysis buffer (40 ml/L of original culture). Lyse cells by sonication on ice (20 min, 5 s on, 10 s off, 35% amplitude) with occasional stirring. 2. Centrifuge the lysate (25 min, 67000g, 4°C). Decant the supernatant. 3. Add 0.6 ml of Ni-sepharose beads to lysate in a 50-ml falcon tube. Mix by rotation for 1 hr in a cold room. 4. Spin lysate with Ni-sepharose beads (700g, 5 min, 4°C). Decant lysate and wash beads with 100 ml Lysis buffer. Repeat wash with 50 ml lysis buffer. Spin again and transfer beads to gravity column in a cold room. 5. Wash column with 20 ml W30. 6. Elute protein with 3x 10 ml EB. Analyse the EB fractions by SDS-PAGE and determine the protein yield using the Bradford assay.
Purification step 2: Size-exclusion chromatography	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Concentrate the protein to 1 ml using a centrifugal concentrator with the appropriate MWCO. 2. Purify the protein further by Size-exclusion chromatography (SEC) on a HiLoad Superdex S200 HR 16/60 column in SEC buffer at 1 ml/min. 3. Analyse fractions by SDS-PAGE. Pool fractions containing protein of desired purity and concentrate to 10-20 mg/ml, as measured by UV spectroscopy. 4. Assess quality of protein by LC-MS intact mass analysis. 5. Snap-freeze aliquots in thin-walled PCR tubes in liquid N₂, and store at -80°C.
Protein yield	9.6 mg/L of culture

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